

EXPLORING THE BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN THE CARE OF THE OLDER ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the benefits and challenges of using technology in the standard of care of older adults utilizing a descriptive quantitative approach. The research focuses on assessing the perceived benefits and challenges of using technology, types of technology used, and level of usage of existing technology in the care of older adults. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire distributed to 80 nurses to three different hospitals in Santiago City, Isabela. Perceived benefits and challenges of using technology, types and familiarity of healthcare technology used were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean scores, percentage, and frequency distributions. The results indicate that the majority of respondents consider healthcare technologies beneficial – particularly Health Information Systems (HIS), and the use of portable, modern diagnostic equipment. These tools are seen as vital in enhancing communication and diagnostics within healthcare settings, allowing healthcare providers to perform their duties more efficiently. On the other hand, the results revealed one of the challenges is even respondents have received sufficient training in using these technologies, many still struggle to apply them effectively in their actual work settings. This suggests that beyond providing training, equal attention must be given to supporting the practical application of new knowledge. The findings have implications for hospital administrators to ensure

nurses to have enough access to technological tools, allowing them to put their training into practice and fully benefit from what they've learned.

Keywords: *Technology, Older adult, Healthcare, Nursing, Health Information Systems*

INTRODUCTION

One of the primary drivers behind transforming elder care is the rapidly aging global population. According to the World Health Organization (2018), "older age" generally refers to individuals aged 60 years and above, which aligns with global trends in defining this life stage. This classification is significant given the rapidly increasing aging population worldwide. It is said that by 2050, it is projected that the number of people aged 60 and older will rise to over 2 billion, making up approximately 22% of the global population. Aging is a normal biological process that leads to the occurrence of age-related diseases. In relation, they become more vulnerable to different chronic diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, kidney diseases, heart diseases, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), arthritis, dementia, and Parkinson's disease.

This significant increase in population creates a greater demand for healthcare services, especially for those managing chronic diseases and seeking quality of life improvements. The traditional way of caring for the elderly is usually done by the families since Filipinos are known for having strong family ties. In a hospital setting, before the existence of the technology, nurses had to do their tasks manually. For example, priming an IV fluid, taking vital signs, and documenting the patient's information and health records; however, some of these practices are still being applied in some hospitals despite the existence of technology. Additionally, traditional care models are increasingly strained to meet the needs of an aging population, especially with a shortage of healthcare professionals, which can lead to delayed care, increasing the risk of complications or hospitalizations that could have been prevented.

Here, technology provides a way to bridge the gap, enabling healthcare providers to manage larger workloads with greater efficiency and allowing for more timely, tailored care that improves patient outcomes. Existing technologies such as Health Monitoring Systems, Electronic Health Records (EHRs), wearable devices like smart watches, assistive technologies like mechanical ventilators, Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP), Bilevel Positive Airway Pressure (BiPAP), and Accuvein have advanced their means of delivering quality care and patient outcomes. The adaptation and utilization of these existing technologies in the care of the older offer healthcare systems a significant opportunity to adopt a proactive approach to predicting health conditions, diagnosing, treating, and monitoring patients both inside and outside hospital settings.

As technology-enabled health services are widely adopted, they empower healthcare systems to implement more flexible care models. Consequently, many conventional methods of delivering health services will be enhanced or gradually replaced by innovative technologies (Kelly *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, adapting and utilizing these existing technologies in nursing practice provides transformation or improvement in the

workflow of the nurses, specifically in terms of health monitoring and documenting data, and performing their responsibilities more safely and efficiently.

However, these innovations in nursing practice also open challenges in the healthcare system and to the professionals. To integrate the technology into practice, nurses and other professionals should have proper awareness, education, and training to ensure patient safety. The cost of training and education about it, and the shortage of professionals in the utilization of technology in practice, burdens the healthcare system.

With that, this study will help to have statistical data on how the integration of technology in the nursing practice affects the workflow of nurses and patient outcomes, specifically in hospitals in Santiago City that integrate technology in their practices. Furthermore, this study will be beneficial to different sectors of healthcare, especially nurses and administrators, for them to assess the benefits and challenges of technology and how they will plan for action to address these adversities. Lastly, elderly patients will also benefit from this study, for it can determine the areas of care that should be maintained and improved in order to have a high standard of care for elderly patients.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex,
 - 1.2. Age,
 - 1.3. Years of experience in nursing service,
 - 1.4. Training on the use of technology,
 - 1.5. Types of technology used in current practice?
2. What is the level of usage of existing technology in the care of older adults?
3. What are the perceived benefits of using existing technology in the care of older adults?
4. What are the perceived challenges of using existing technology in the care of older adults?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researchers utilized a descriptive method, a type of quantitative research in the process of exploring the benefits and challenges of technology in the care of the older adult. The study focused on 80 selected registered nurses who have experienced the integration of technological advancement in healthcare using Purposive Sampling technique to ensure validity. Thus, the researchers have purposely set a criterion in narrowing down the characteristics of the respondents, which are the following:

1. The participant should be a registered nurse;
2. Has at least 1 year of experience in the nursing service;
3. The participant should be working in hospital facilities within Santiago City, Isabela that utilize healthcare technologies (e.g., EHRs, health monitoring devices, wearable devices); and
4. The participant should be working or have rotated to areas of the intensive care unit, medical ward, and private rooms.

Below is the table showing the population and the sample sizes.

Distribution of Respondents

Hospital	Population	Size	Percent
Hospital A	30	25	31.25
Hospital B	30	25	31.25
Hospital C	40	30	37.50
TOTAL	100	80	100.00

The study was conducted in Santiago City, located in the province of Isabela, specifically within hospitals. The researchers have selected three hospitals for their study. These hospitals are recognized for their use of advanced technology, including health monitoring systems, electronic health records, wearable devices, electronic devices, and telehealth. The research instrument used in this study is a researcher-made survey questionnaire that uses a Likert scale. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize respondent demographics, types of technology used in practice, and familiarity with healthcare technology. The researchers prepared informed consent and strictly observed data confidentiality for ethical considerations. The study provided valuable insights to enhance patient's quality of life for older adults and healthcare outcomes as technology continues to evolve in response to their unique needs.

RESULTS

Table 1. Profile of Respondents as to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	19	23.75
Female	61	76.25
TOTAL	80	100.00

Table 2. Profile of Respondents as to Age

Age Range	Frequency	Percent
22-25	33	41.25
26-29	10	12.50
30-33	10	12.50
34-37	17	21.25

38-41	9	11.25
41 and above	1	1.25
TOTAL	80	100.00

Table 3. Profile of Respondents as to Years of Experience in Nursing Service

Years of Experience	Frequency	Percent
1-3 years	44	55.00
4-6 years	12	15.00
7-9 years	10	12.50
10-12 years	7	8.75
13-15 years	3	3.75
16 years and above	4	5.00
TOTAL	80	100.00

Table 4. Frequency of Training on the Use of Existing Technologies in Healthcare

Frequency of Training	Frequency	Percentage
Every 3 months	27	33.75
Every 6 months	38	47.50
Once a year	14	17.50
Never	1	1.25
TOTAL	80	100.00

Table 5. Types of Technology Used in Current Practice

Technology Used	Frequency of Mention	Percent
1. Health Monitoring Systems	73	91.25
2. Electronic Health Records (EHR)	18	22.50

3. Wearable Devices	21	26.25
4. Assistive Technologies	46	57.50
5. Diagnostic Equipment	42	52.50
6. Infusion and Medication Delivery Systems	63	78.75

Table 6. Level of Usage of Technology in the Care of the Older Adult

Particulars	Mean	Interpretation
1. I use health monitoring systems in my work in caring for older adults on a daily basis.	3.40	Always
2. I use a central monitoring system for faster communication and more effective patient care.	3.21	Most of the Time
3. I use Electronic Health Record (EHR) in documenting data of my patients.	2.24	Seldom
4. My patients use wearable devices to keep track of their health status, both inside and outside the hospital.	2.25	Seldom
5. I use assistive technologies in the area of my work on a daily basis.	3.10	Most of the Time
6. Diagnostic equipment is readily available when I need to use it.	3.23	Most of the Time
7. I use an IV infusion pump/ syringe pump to prime IV fluids for my patients.	3.40	Always
Overall Mean	2.98	Most of the Time

Table 7. Perceived Benefits of Existing Technologies in Healthcare in Caring for Older Adults

Particulars	Mean	Interpretation
1. Existing technologies in the care of older adults reduce my manual workload.	3.11	Agree
2. Electronic Health Record helps me to prevent errors in documenting the data of patients.	2.91	Agree
3. I can easily track the data and health status of my patients through the use of EHRs.	2.80	Agree
4. Health monitoring systems provide me with more accurate and continuous monitoring of my patient's health status.	3.19	Agree
5. With the help of the existing technologies, my physical and emotional stress decreases.	3.13	Agree
6. I get to focus more on my patients due to the decreased manual workloads through the help of technology.	3.19	Agree
7. Portable and latest diagnostic equipment helps me to determine the health status of my patients.	3.26	Strongly Agree
8. Health Information System (HIS) helps me to build a more effective way of communication with other health care professionals.	3.31	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.11	Agree

Table 8. Perceived Challenges of Technology in the Care of Older Adults

Particulars	Mean	Interpretation
1. It is difficult for me to use the technological tools in my practice.	2.64	Agree
2. It is difficult for me to adapt to the utilization of technological tools due to my age.	2.15	Disagree
3. I have received adequate training on how to use these technologies in my practice.	3.04	Agree
4. I don't find the significance of being well-informed and trained in using the existing technologies in my practice.	2.11	Disagree
5. I don't attend seminars and training regarding the utilization of technologies due to their cost.	2.20	Disagree
6. I know how to troubleshoot technological tools when they suddenly malfunction.	2.86	Agree
Overall Mean	2.09	Disagree

DISCUSSION

Table 1

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on sex. The data indicate that out of the total sample, 61 respondents or 76.25% were female, indicating a majority, whereas 19 respondents or 23.75% were male.

The predominance of female respondents aligns with global and local trends in nursing, where women continue to dominate the profession. A study by Cruz et al. (2020) highlights that in the Philippines, approximately 75% of nurses are female, largely due to traditional caregiving roles and societal expectations. Similarly, the World Health Organization (2021) reported that women represent nearly 80% of the nursing workforce worldwide, emphasizing the need for gender diversity initiatives in healthcare professions.

Table 2

Table 2 displays the distribution of respondents according to age. The highest proportion of respondents falls within the 22–25 age group, accounting for 33 or 41.25% of the total sample. In contrast, the lowest representation is observed in the 41 and above category, comprising only 1 or 1.25% of the respondents.

The significant presence of respondents aged 22–25 suggests that a younger workforce dominates the nursing profession, particularly in elderly care. According to Santos et al. (2021), newly licensed nurses in the Philippines typically enter the workforce between the ages of 22 and 25, influenced by the country's education and licensure system. This trend highlights the need for continuous professional development programs tailored for younger nurses to enhance their competencies in handling older adult patients.

Table 3

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of respondents based on their years of experience in nursing service. The majority of respondents have 1–3 years of experience, representing 44 or 55.00% of the total sample. Meanwhile, the least represented group consists of those with 13–15 years of experience, accounting for only 3 or 3.75%.

The prevalence of nurses with 1–3 years of experience suggests a workforce composed mainly of early-career professionals. According to De Guzman and Reyes (2022), the high turnover rate among Filipino nurses, driven by migration and job dissatisfaction, results in a younger, less experienced workforce in local healthcare settings. This highlights the necessity of retention strategies and mentorship programs to support novice nurses in developing their skills, particularly in elderly care. In addition, this finding shows that younger generations are most likely adaptable to technology. According to the study of Tan and Chin (2023), Generation Y and Generation Z are widely regarded as the most technologically proficient generations. Generation Y, having grown up during the emergence of digital technology, formed the first wave of the digital era, while Generation Z was born into a world where advanced technology was already deeply integrated into daily life—allowing both groups to adapt quickly to new technological advancements.

Table 4

Table 4 presents the distribution of respondents based on the frequency of training they receive on the use of existing technologies in healthcare. The highest proportion of respondents undergo training occasionally, or every six months, making up 38 or 47.50% of the total sample. In contrast, the lowest percentage is observed among those who have never received training, accounting for only 1 or 1.25%.

The predominance of occasional training suggests that while technology integration in healthcare is recognized, training sessions remain infrequent. According to

Mendoza and Cruz (2021), periodic training every six months is a common practice in healthcare institutions to balance operational demands and continuous skill enhancement. Their finding highlights the importance of more frequent training programs to ensure that nurses remain proficient in using healthcare technologies, ultimately improving patient care outcomes.

Table 5

Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents based on the types of technology used in their current practice. The most commonly utilized technology is health monitoring systems, reported by 73 or 91.25% of respondents. In contrast, electronic health records (EHR) are the least used, with only 18 or 22.50% of respondents incorporating them into their practice.

The widespread use of health monitoring systems highlights their essential role in patient care, particularly for continuous monitoring of vital signs in older adults. According to Santos et al. 2020, advanced health monitoring technologies have become standard in healthcare settings due to their ability to provide real-time data, improving early detection of complications and patient outcomes. This finding underscores the necessity of investing in these systems and ensuring healthcare professionals receive proper training to maximize their benefits. On the other hand, Electronic Health Records (EHR) help in documenting the data of patients, as well as ensuring more accurate data and coordination with other healthcare professionals. According to De Mesa et al (2023), self-efficacy is the emerging key factor influencing the intention of nurses to use the EHR system. This implies that users are more inclined to adopt the technology when they feel confident in their ability to use it effectively and carry out their responsibilities.

Table 6

Table 6 presents the respondents' level of technology usage in the care of older adults. The highest mean score of 3.40, interpreted as "Always," is observed in two areas: "I use health monitoring systems in my work in caring for older adults on a daily basis" and "I use IV infusion pump/syringe pump in priming IV fluids of my patients," while the lowest mean score of 2.24, interpreted as "Seldom," is found in the item "I use Electronic Health Record (EHR) in documenting data of my patients." The overall mean score of 2.98, categorized as "Most of the Time," indicates that technology is generally used in the respondents' practices, but not consistently across all tools.

The frequent use of health monitoring systems and IV infusion pumps underscores the significant role these technologies play in the daily care of older adults. Health monitoring systems are essential in continuously tracking patients' vital signs, enabling early detection of any health issues and timely interventions, which is particularly critical for older adults who often face multiple health risks. Similarly, IV infusion pumps ensure precise administration of fluids, which is vital in managing older patients who are at higher risk for dehydration or fluid imbalances. Research has shown that these technologies contribute to improved patient safety and the overall quality of care (Sloot et al., 2021).

The consistent use of these tools highlights their importance in maintaining optimal health outcomes in older adults.

Table 7

Table 7 presents the respondents' perceived benefits of existing technologies in the healthcare of older adults. The highest mean score of 3.31, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," is observed in the item "Health Information System (HIS) helps me to build a more effective way of communication to other healthcare professionals," followed closely by "Portable and latest diagnostic equipment helps me to determine the health status of my patients," with a mean score of 3.26, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." The lowest mean score of 2.80, interpreted as "Agree," is found in the item "I can easily track the data and health status of my patients through the use of EHRs." The overall mean score of 3.11, categorized as "Agree," indicates that, overall, respondents perceive the benefits of existing technologies in improving patient care and easing their workload.

The highest mean scores for the use of Health Information Systems (HIS) and portable diagnostic equipment emphasize the significant impact of these technologies on enhancing communication and diagnostics in healthcare settings. HIS helps streamline communication between healthcare professionals, facilitating quicker and more accurate exchanges of patient information, which is essential in providing coordinated and efficient care (Jiang et al., 2022). Similarly, the use of portable diagnostic equipment supports timely assessments of patient health, allowing for more accurate and immediate decision-making, which is particularly important in the care of older adults who may require rapid interventions. The consistent endorsement of these technologies highlights their importance in improving both the efficiency of healthcare delivery and the quality of care provided to older adults.

Table 8

Table 8 presents the respondents' perceived challenges of technology in the care of older adults. The results show that the most challenging aspect for the nurses in using the technology in the care of the adults is found in the statement, "It is difficult for me to use the technological tools in my practice," with a mean of 2.64, interpreted as "Agree".

According to Lorenzo et al. (2024), key enablers of effective training include a supportive work environment that provides a schedule allowing for both professional development and work-life balance. Equally important is a positive learning culture where colleagues and supervisors actively encourage continuous training and innovation. Additionally, access to a stable internet connection and adequate equipment is essential to ensure full participation in courses and timely submission of deliverables. This finding highlights that, even with sufficient training, successful implementation in the field requires adapting the acquired knowledge and skills to the area of work.

Conclusions

1. The researchers found that the majority of the respondents were female, accounting for 76.25% of the total sample, while males comprised 23.75%. Most of the nurses who participated in the study were aged 22–25 years, making up 41.25% of the total sample. In contrast, the lowest representation was observed among nurses aged 41 and above, with only 1.25%. Regarding years of experience, the majority of respondents had 1–3 years of nursing service, representing 55.00% of the sample. Meanwhile, the least represented group was those with 13–15 years of experience, accounting for 3.75%. Findings show that the highest proportion of respondents undergo training occasionally or every six months, making up 47.50% of the sample. In contrast, only 1.25% reported never having received training. It was noted that the most commonly utilized technology is health monitoring systems, reported by 91.25% of respondents. In contrast, Electronic Health Records (EHRs) are the least used, with only 22.50% incorporating them into their practice.
2. Based on the descriptive summary of the levels of technology usage in the care of older adults, the findings revealed that the highest levels of usage were observed in health monitoring systems and IV infusion/syringe pumps, both with a mean score of 3.40, interpreted as "Always." In contrast, the use of Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and wearable devices for patients had the lowest mean score of 2.24, indicating they were used "Seldom," and with an overall mean score of 2.98, categorized as "Most of the Time".
3. The findings revealed that the perceived benefits of existing technologies in healthcare are reflected in the item "Health Information System (HIS) helps me to build a more effective way of communication with other healthcare professionals," followed closely by "Portable and latest diagnostic equipment helps me to determine the health status of my patients," both with a mean score of 3.26, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." The lowest mean score of 2.80, interpreted as "Agree," was found in the item "I can easily track the data and health status of my patients through the use of EHRs". The overall mean score is 3.11, categorized as "Agree".
4. The respondents' perceived challenges in using technology in the care of older adults were assessed. The highest mean score of 3.04, interpreted as "Agree," was observed in the item "I have received adequate training on how to use these technologies in my practice."

Recommendations

The integration of technology into the care of older adults presents both significant opportunities and considerable challenges. To maximize the benefits and mitigate the risks, a multi-pronged approach involving future nurses, healthcare administrators, and researchers is essential. This requires a commitment to continuous professional

development for nurses, strategic investment in technological infrastructure by administrators, and innovative research to inform effective training programs. The following recommendations address these key areas to improve the quality and efficacy of care for this vulnerable population.

Nurses should actively participate in continuing education opportunities focused on healthcare technologies relevant to older adult care. Consistent attendance at seminars and workshops, coupled with the proactive application of learned skills in their daily practice, will allow nurses to optimize the benefits and address the challenges of technology integration, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

Healthcare administrators should invest in upgrading and providing essential technological equipment to enhance the care of older adults. This includes supporting nurses' participation in relevant training programs and ensuring they have access to the necessary tools to effectively apply their newly acquired skills in practice. This investment will directly improve patient care and outcomes while addressing the benefits and challenges of technology use in older adult care.

Future researchers should leverage this study's findings to develop and promote targeted training programs focused on the effective use of technology in the care of older adults. This will help equip nurses with the necessary skills and knowledge to harness technology's benefits while mitigating associated challenges, ultimately improving patient care.

Through this approach, healthcare institutions will be able to deliver better care to older adults and, therefore, achieve a better quality of life for everyone, realizing the promise of older adult care made possible by the use of technology.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In seeking consent from participants, the researchers prepared a consent letter to ensure that each respondent clearly understood their voluntary involvement. This letter served as a formal agreement, allowing participants to freely join or withdraw from the study at any time. Additionally, each participant was thoroughly informed about the purpose of the research, helping them grasp its significance and feel valued in the process. The study was designed to ensure participants are protected from any potential harm, whether physical, such as injury, or psychological, such as undue stress. Creating a respectful, comfortable, and safe environment is a priority to support everyone's well-being throughout the research.

To respect participants' time, discussions have focused strictly on topics relevant to the study. Furthermore, the researchers are committed to upholding strict confidentiality and anonymity for all participants, particularly during data collection. Every piece of information shared by respondents will be handled with integrity, ensuring it is neither filtered nor altered. Before any interview or questionnaire is conducted, the researchers have thoroughly explained the intent and goals of the study, seeking explicit

permission to proceed. In terms of writing technicalities, the researchers are careful to avoid plagiarism and no AI generated statements by properly citing and crediting all sources, respecting the original authors' intellectual contributions.

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